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Pages: 17-400

Part II:

Teaching: The new ways of teaching: contents. The new ways of teaching: strategies. Fieldwork in the classrooms and theoretical framework. ICTs: Literacy and digital culture and new educational policies. Literacy and digital culture and new educational policies. Flipped Classroom, Gamification, E- Learning, M-learning Blended Learning.

Pages: 417-1002

Part III:

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Pages: 1011-1314

Part IV:

Innovation: University news: publications of excellence and doctoral work. Social networks, 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0. Emerging themes in Social Sciences, Arts and Humanities. Innovating in pure Sciences. Models and results of entrepreneurship.

Pages: 1323-1536

Part V:

Investigation:

Lines of research: Work and projects. Research and researchers: models of works, analysis, bibliometrics and future. The latest in non-regulated investigations. Investigating in Pure Sciences and Health.

Pages: 1541-1655

Part VI

Miscellany:

Prospective and Systemic. New áreas.

Pages: 1659-1698

Part VII

Digital and Information Literacy

Pages: 1701-1711

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Origin and evolution of the creation of spanish universities from the 12th century until the approval of the national quality assessment plan

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Abstract: In recent years there has been talk about the future of the Spanish University since the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon in 2010 and the University Strategy of 2015. Authors such as Antonio Pulido (2007), Saturnino de la Plaza (2003), R. Roda Aixendri (2003), Emilio Fíntela (2002) or Francesc Solá (2002) talk about it. The origin of the University was caused by the avalanche of scholars seeking knowledge, which allowed the beginning of a new historical era, breaking the molds of the monastic and cathedral schools and gave rise to a permanent institution of teaching (Jiménez, 1971) [1]. Important the work carried out by the students we see that it is repeated with the European Higher Education Area where a student-centered learning is requested, the mobility of students and teachers, attention to permanent education, quality improvement through external evaluations and enhance the international appeal (Pulido, 2007) [2].

Keywords: origin of the university – Spanish universities – senior colleges – novator – national quality assessment plan

1 Introduction

In the twelfth century, the avalanche of scholars seeking knowledge allowed the beginning of a new historical era breaking the molds of the monastic and cathedral schools and gave rise to a permanent institution of education as was the creation of universities (Jiménez, 1971) [1]. "The appearance of medieval institutions known as Studies or Universities was a consequence of the intellectual renaissance of the twelfth century" (Jiménez, 197, p. 11) [1].

At the end of the twelfth century there were four centers of study in Europe, Salerno, Bologna, Oxford and Paris, among which students could choose between medicine, law, theology or humanities. In 1212, Alfonso VIII of Castile founded the General Study of Palencia, in 1215 the one of Salamanca was created by Alfonso IX of León and that of Valladolid in 1260. In Lérida the foundation of the University was by the king don Jaime II of Aragón, King Don Sancho IV gave in 1293 a privilege for which he ordered to establish General Studies in Alcala de Henares. For the Studies of Valladolid, Don Alfonso XI indicated an endowment, thus the sustenance of the Study and the payment of professors was on account of the Council. In 1350, King Don Pedro the Ceremonious created the University of Perpignan and the University of Huesca in 1354, but neither of them succeeded. Finally, the Lisbon University - Coimbra is created by the king. "Alcalá with almost 4,000 new registrations, Coimbra approaching 3,000, Salamanca reaching 7,000 enrolled or Valladolid around 2,000 before the 1595 plague" (Rubio Muñoz, 2014, p. 408) [3]. The characteristic of these universities is that their foundation is of real origin and not, pontifical due to its legal tradition Roman-pago and in its essence, importance was given to law studies (Jimenez, 1971) [1]. King Alfonso X the Wise in 1254 promulgated in Toledo the organization of the university, which is known by the Magna Carta of the University of Salamanca, and gave its first economic endowment.

But with the passage of time, education became an expensive burden and passed into the hands of the Church. The royal power did not provide fixed income to attend the Studies, so in the middle of the 13th century, the Universities of Paris, Bologna, Oxford and Salamanca were considered from the Catholic world.

The Church founded major colleges throughout Spanish territory. These six schools were the following: (Aguilar Piñal, 1967) San Bartolomé el Viejo in Salamanca imitating that of Bologna, Santa Cruz de Valladolid in 1480, San Ildefonso de Alcalá in 1500, Cuenca in Salamanca and the of San Salvador, called Oviedo. They were the ruin of Spanish universities. In 1766 the collegial turn in the Salamanca chairs was suppressed and then, the company of Jesus was expelled. During the reign of Carlos III the Olavide Plan was created. His curriculum was based "on the right balance between the traditional and the modern, between authority and freedom. The Faculties are respected, but the extension of the teachings is requested; foreign textbooks of an acceptable modernity are proposed; the authority of the Rector is reinforced and the professors are commanded to comply with their obligations" (Aguilar Piñal, 2003, p. 41) [5]. It is with the arrival of King Carlos III and Olavide's plan when university directors are appointed to ministers to report on their situation and ensure their reforms even going so far as to suppress them, leaving only 11 universities in 1807.

New institutions were created in letters and in sciences and academies as "the result of the institutionalization of private gatherings or logical development of already existing nuclei of the Austrias" (Vernet Ginés, 1998, p. 145) [6]. In the reign of Carlos II (1665-1670) the movement "novator" denounced the Spanish scientific backwardness. This movement was developed throughout the seventeenth century, at the end of the century, in Zaragoza, Valencia, Barcelona and Madrid, having a recovery of scientific production. These novators were grouped in gatherings or around patrons to discuss the findings and test new inventions. They created a manifesto called the Philosophical Letter, *medicochymica* by Juan de Cabriada where "he made a plea in favor of the new science, experimental knowledge and the art of anatomizing nature" (López-Ocón Cabrera, 2003, p. 124) [7].

2 Problem Formulations

Knowing the history of the Spanish University allows you to appreciate the great progress that this institution has undergone over the centuries since its creation in the 12th century with the appearance of four centers of Studies, Salerno, Bologna, Oxford and Paris among the which, the students could choose between medicine, laws, theology or humanities [1].

Its decadent evolution has passed between centuries of leverage before any type of change until the arrival of the first Bourbons. This institution created by the lack of bureaucrats to take the reins of power and by which through training in them allowed it, was for years stagnant and anchored in the simple transmission of the translation of classical texts, based on the figure of authority without allowing the entry of new science defended by the novator movement.

Through this article the evolution of the Spanish University is made known; looking back we can see the trajectory of this institution to know where it is going in the future with the approval of the National Quality Plan and the Treaty of Lisbon in 2010.

3 Conclusion

The European Higher Education Area calls for student-centered learning, mobility of students and teachers, attention to lifelong education, improvement of quality and external evaluations and enhancing international attractiveness according to Antonio Pulido. The "techno-utopians" warn of the decline of the University if it continues with the master classes and fixed posts for life, inabilities to serve a new world of mass audience and instant information in front of the "cultural conservatives" who affirm that It is a mistake in higher education for people who confuse to pursue the truth with seeking the benefit (Pulido, 2007) [2]. In this way, Saturnino de la Plaza speaks that can reach a strong process of competitiveness, since there is a binomial of the university of autonomy, social responsibility that can affect the accreditation of studies and public funding such as the start-up for example, the National Quality Assessment Plan (2003) [8]. Another author, R. Roda Aixendri considers that the society of knowledge of an activity oriented to the realization, diffusion, transfer, ... in the way that requires it to man is no longer the execution of a series of tasks prescribed within a predetermined area, the creativity necessary to face the problems in the framework of

unpredictable development, the same being the first factor of innovation (2003) [9]. Emilio Fíntela considers the use of Internet as the key element in the development of the University where it is used in distance education. This new educational education reduces the cost of training per student by more than 50% (2002) [10]. In the opinion of Francesc Solá, the university must serve students over the age of eighteen seeking a second degree and where this institution no longer has the exclusivity of higher education, as other centers may have knowledge, usually private or via red (2002) [11].

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